

Early diagnosis of covid-associated cavernous sinus thrombosis

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Abstract. Covid-associated cavernous sinus thrombosis is one of the actual topics in neurology, and an increase in the number of patients with this diagnosis during a pandemic means the relevance of this theme. In the scientific work, 22 (100%) patients were examined, of which 11 (50 %) were men, 11 (50%) were women. The paper analyzes the data of clinical and laboratory-instrumental studies, develops an algorithm for diagnosing this pathology, and gives recommendations for application in the field of practical medicine.

Key words: Covid-19, cavernous sinus thrombosis, ophthalmoplegia, neuropathy of oculomotor nerves, Syndrome of Toloso-Hunt , Mucormycosis.

1. Introduction

Observations showed that during the pandemic in Uzbekistan, more than 300 patients became ill with Covid-associated cavernous sinus thrombosis (CST1). With this nosology, 60-70% of patients died, and almost all of them ended with amavrosis (loss of vision). For comparison, before the pandemic, the number of these patients was rare across the country. The complexity and atypical clinical course of this pathological process make its diagnosis difficult. The sharp increase in the level of morbidity during the period of Covid-19 and the continuation of the pandemic indicate the relevance of this pathology and the need to pay special attention to it, prevent further complications, and develop its differential diagnosis criteria. The aim of this paper is improving early diagnostic criteria for covid-associated cavernous sinus thrombosis.

2. Materials and methods

Characteristics of patients. In this article, the results of clinical and neurological changes in 22 patients with clinical conditions accompanied by symptoms of ophthalmoplegia, ptosis, chemosis, amaurosis, anisocoria and sensory disturbances in the face, treated in various treatment and prevention institutions of Tashkent from June 2021 to January 2022 stated. Observed patients are divided by gender as follows: 11 of them (50%) are women, 11 (50%) are men. According to WHO 2016 classification, 6 patients (27.27%) are middle-aged (45-59), 14 (63.36%) are aged (60-74), and 2 (9.09%) are elderly. (75-90) years old. Diabetes mellitus, hypertension and BTTK2 were identified as competing diseases in the observed patients.

The following clinical and laboratory methods were used in order to study clinical and neurological changes in patients under observation and to develop criteria for early diagnosis of KST:

- 1) Anamnesis collection.
- 2) Study of patient complaints.
- 3) Checking neurostatus dynamically.
- 4) Rhinoscopy.

- 5) General blood analysis analysis.
- 6) Coagulogram.
- 7) MRI or MSCT examination.
- 8) IFA and PCR.

3. Results and discussion

In the anamnesis of all observed patients, specific treatment against Covid-19 and diabetes mellitus, hypertension and CKD were identified as competing diseases. When the complaints of the patients under observation were analyzed, the following was determined. Patients have reduced or complete loss of vision in the right or left eye, increased body temperature, pain in the face, swelling and various sensory disturbances, and the above symptoms, such as discharge from the nose of a different nature 90 found in % cases; 10% of patients complained of headaches, epileptic seizures, general weakness, sleep disorders and memory loss.

As a result of objective examination, in Neurostatus: 50% of patients developed amblyopia or amaurosis as a result of damage to the II pair of cranial nerves; In the remaining 50% of patients, it was found that, in addition to amblyopia and amaurosis, loss of pupillary reflexes is the result of damage to the II pair of cerebral nerves; Almost all patients were diagnosed with total ophthalmoplegia as a result of damage to the nerves moving the eye (III, IV, VI); Hypoesthesia was detected in the field of n.ophthalmicus innervation of V pair of nerves.

In rhinoscopy: 60% of patients had purulent secretions in the nasal passages, and 40% had black necrotic masses.

The following was revealed in the laboratory tests: When the general blood analysis was studied, an increase in the number of leukocytes, a shift of the leukoformula to the left, and a slight increase in the erythrocyte sedimentation rate were observed in the majority of patients. An increase in the number of eosinophils was observed in 7 patients. When comparing the blood analysis of patients with CST with the analyzes of the control group (confirmed Covid-19 infection, without CST), it was found that there was no reliable difference. When the amount of fibrinogen in the blood was studied, in patients with CST, this indicator ranged from 177 mg/% to 1650 mg/%, that is, the average amount was 485.4 ± 61.7 , while the average amount in the control group was 306.1 ± 12.9 , that is, the amount of fibrinogen increased reliably ($p < 0.01$); PTI in patients averaged $94 \pm 3.2\%$, and an increasing trend was observed in comparison to the control group; Thrombotest index in patients with CST is mostly around V-VII, while in the control group it is III-IV, changes may be of specific importance; In patients whose blood procalcitonin was studied, the changes ranged from 0.2 ng/ml to 0.69 ng/ml, which can be said to be typical for KST; In the MRI and MSCT examinations of the patients, 19 patients had blood clots in the sinus area, brain tumor, hyperdense foci and symptoms of pansinusitis; The possibility of presence of mucormycosis was determined by rhinoscopy, and in 27.3% of patients, mucormycosis fungus was observed to grow into the vascular endothelium, and coagulopathy was also detected in almost all of them.

As an example, two different clinical conditions with the above symptoms and changes in the results of laboratory-instrumental examinations are given below:

Clinical Status

Patient M., 50 years old, on 04.08.2021 through the Emergency Brigade (TYB) to the intensive care department of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy, building 9, due to increased body temperature, shortness of breath, severe pain in the left eyelid area, left facial area was hospitalized with complaints of swelling and general weakness. According to his anamnesis, he thinks he has been sick for a month. On 05.07.2021 "Coronavirus infection Covid-19 (Confirmed) Moderately severe course. Out-of-hospital bilateral pneumonia". Yondosh: "GK3 II AG4 II Risk III and Diabetes mellitus" was treated in the hospital of infectious diseases. In the hospital, he received 5000 IU of heparin twice a day and clopedagril 75 mg once a day; On 07/28/2021, he consulted an ophthalmologist with redness and swelling in his left eye. Ophthalmologist's conclusion: Left-sided myositis,

conjunctival chemosis and acute reactive edema. A neurologist and ENT consultation was recommended. The patient was hospitalized due to the increase of the above complaints and deterioration of his condition; The general condition of the patient is moderate. Consciousness is clear. Status is active. Body temperature 38.5 0 C. AQB-150/90 mm.sm.us P-s 108 dice/min, SpO2=88 %. Neurostatus: BMN Movement of the eyeballs: OS- total ophthalmoplegia, OD- full size, no nystagmus, no diplopia. Pupils are S>D, reaction to light is preserved. Valle I, II, III points are painful on the left side. Hypesthesia on the face according to Zelder's zones. There is no deviation. At rest, the face is symmetrical. The lower and upper facial muscles are symmetrical. Gain reflex-stored D=S. Muscle strength 5 points normatonus D=S. The coordinator performs the tests correctly. Can stand in Romberg position. The function of the pelvic organs is not disturbed. Root withdrawal symptoms- negative. Pathological reflexes - bilateral Marinesko-Radovich positive D=S. Meningeal symptoms-negative.

Neurologist's diagnosis

Covid-associated cavernous sinus thrombosis

The patient was recommended by a neurologist to undergo a brain CT scan for the purpose of diagnosis. Analyzes 05.08.2021 General blood analysis: Erythrocytes- 2.9*10¹²/l, Hemoglobin- 82 g/l, Leukocytes-5.7*10⁹/l, Platelets 184*10⁹/l, ECHT-20 mm/s. 08/05/2021 Coagulogram: Fibrinogen-421 mg D-dimer- 496 ng/ml, PV- 16.4 sec, ACHTV-19.6 sec, PTI- 99%, MNO- 0.9. Procalcitonin -0.6 ng/ml. General urinalysis - no changes. X-ray of chest organs 03.08.2021- Bilateral pneumonia. EKG- Rhythm sinusoidal, 95 bpm, right-shifted. Metabolic changes in the myocardium.

Clinical diagnosis

Main: Covid-19, severe.

Competitor: GK II AG II Risk III and Diabetes.

Complication: Bilateral interstitial pneumonia (30%). Cavernous sinus thrombosis.

10.08.2021. Further analyzes were carried out. Coagulogram: Fibrinogen-377 mg D-dimer- 680 ng/ml, PV- 16.1 sec, ACHTV-25.4 sec, PTI- 89%, MNO- 1.21.

The patient was under the supervision of a neurologist, depending on the dynamics of clinical and laboratory changes, the diagnosis of "Covid-associated cavernous sinus thrombosis" was confirmed.

Clinical Status

Patient I., 48 years old, was sent to the Intensive Care Unit of the 3rd multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy through the Ambulance Brigade on 10.01.2022, with an increase in body temperature, discharge of black discharge from the nose, vision in the right eye. He was admitted with complaints of loss of vision and headache. Anamnesis from 15.06.2021 to 30.06.2021 "Coronavirus infection Covid-19 (Confirmed) Moderate course. Out-of-hospital bilateral pneumonia". Yondosh: "Diagnosed with diabetes, he was treated at the hospital for infectious diseases."

The general condition of the patient is moderate-severe. Hushi is in a state of soporosis. The condition is passive. Body temperature is 38.0 0 C. AQB-100/60 mm.sm.us P-s 90-100 dice/min, SpO2=95%. In neurostatus: BMN Movement of the eyeballs: OS- total ophthalmoplegia, OD- total ophthalmoplegia, diplopia-no. Vis OD/OS=0.0/1.0. Pupils are S<D, reaction to light is not preserved. Valle I, II, III points are painful on the right side. The perception of the face according to Zelder's zones is preserved. There is no deviation. At rest, the face is symmetrical. The lower and upper facial muscles are symmetrical. Gain reflex-stored D=S. Muscle strength 5 points normatonus D=S. The coordinator performs the tests correctly. Can stand in Romberg position. The function of the pelvic organs is not disturbed. Root withdrawal symptoms- negative. Pathological reflexes - bilateral Marinesko-Radovich positive D=S. Meningeal symptoms-negative.

Neurologist's diagnosis

Cavernous sinus and A.optahmica thrombosis with Mucormycosis etiology?

The patient was recommended by a neurologist to undergo MRI-angiography of the brain for the purpose of diagnosis.

Analyzes 06.06.2021 General blood analysis: Erythrocytes- $3.9 \cdot 10^{12}/l$, Hemoglobin- 92 g/l, Leukocyte- $6.7 \cdot 10^9/l$, Platelets $254 \cdot 10^9/l$, ECHT-30 mm/s. 08/05/2021 Coagulogram: Fibrinogen-432 mg D-dimer- 446 ng/ml, PV- 18.4 sec, ACHTV-17.6 sec, PTI- 100%, MNO- 0.8. Procalcitonin -0.5 ng/ml.

General urinalysis - no changes. X-ray of chest organs 05/10/2021- Bilateral pneumonia. EKG- Rhythm sinusoidal, 88 bpm, right-shifted. Metabolic changes in the myocardium.

ENT examination: Cavernous sinus thrombosis with mucormycosis etiology?

Ophthalmologist examination: Thrombosis of the right eye artery?

07.06.2021. Conclusion of MRT-angiography examination: No organic and pathological changes were detected in the brain. Sphenoiditis, ethmoiditis, right-sided sinusitis (mucormycosis etiology?). Thrombosis of the right eye artery.

Clinical diagnosis

Primary post-Covid-19 condition.

Competitor: Diabetes mellitus type 2 severe decompensation stage (10 years), Bronchial asthma infectious allergic form.

Complication: cavernous sinus and right eye artery thrombosis.

4. Conclusions

Summarizing the results of clinical and laboratory-instrumental examinations, it can be noted that changes in coagulogram parameters in KST patients - fibrinogen amount, increase of PTI, increase of procalcitonin index in blood and infection with mucormycosis fungi are typical for this pathology.

Diagnostic criteria for covid-associated cavernous sinus:

- The patients are mainly aged (60-74) and old (75-90);
- Neurostatus in patients with KST - presence of laboratory changes characteristic of KST, such as ophthalmoplegia, amaurosis or amblyopia, preserved or not preserved pupillary reflexes;
- Presence of diabetes, hypertension, connective tissue systemic diseases as competing diseases;
- presence of signs of coagulopathy- (increased amount of fibrinogen, increased PTI) in laboratory tests;
- An increase in the amount of procalcitonin, which is an indicator of bacterial damage;
- Presence of mucormycosis fungus in the nasal passages and adjacent cavities during rhinoscopy.

Recommendations for application to practical medicine.

1. To bring to the attention of practicing doctors that KST is one of the serious complications that can develop in patients with Covid-19.
2. Apply diagnostic methods from the obtained results (fibrinogen, PTI, procalcitonin, rhinoscopy) for early diagnosis of Covid-associated CST.
3. Development of optimal ways of correction of the changes that caused its development (increase in the amount of fibronogen, PTI and procalcitonin) in the treatment of patients with KST and their application to practical medicine.
4. Additions to the standards of diagnosis and treatment of Covid-19 in the established order, taking into account the results obtained.

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